

The Relation Of Orang Basudara To Unite Muslims And Christians Of Siri Sori In Saparua Island, Maluku

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 01, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: August 17, 2020</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Relation, History, Culture, Orang Basudara</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3990419</p>	<p><i>This article aims to explore the relation of the Muslims and Christians of Siri Sori, which are built on the foundation of history-culture as orang basudara. The fraternal relationship which becomes the adhesive of the different religious communities becomes a unifying capital, even though they have experienced conflicts of religion. This article was written using the historical method as a guideline for implementation and technical instructions about the material, criticism, interpretation, and presentation of history. The operationalization of the historical method was intended to collect, manage, and use these sources as data in the construction of this paper. The source of data of this study was from historical and cultural documents of the Muslims and Christian of Siri Sori in Saparua, which was found in the documentations of the governances of the both villages and the interviews conducted with the relevant informants for the purpose of explaining this paper comprehensively. The results of this explanation show that the history of the fraternity of the Muslims and Christians of Siri Sori has influenced the formation of the peaceful relationship between the two and contributed peace in Moluccas.</i></p>

Introduction

Maluku people have a strong culture to maintain ethnic unity, regardless of religious differences due to the arrival of Islam and Christianity between them. This condition is revealed by the proof, for example, there are Ambonese in Central Maluku. In the eyes of the Ambonese, the same traditional foundation between Islam and Christianity blurring the two religions differences. The great division conflict between them can be avoided by glorifying their cultural similarities. It emphasized that these similarities led to harmonize Muslim and Christian communities with their traditional belief systems.

The media used to strengthen inter-communal unity is *pela-gandong*, namely fraternal relations based on blood relations between two or more countries. Dieter Bartels argues that *pela* is the basis of Ambonese ethnic identity and symbolic Muslim-Christian unity which has an aura of holiness for ordinary people, especially in villages. R. Dandirwalu revealed that *pela* is a friendship between Muslim and Christian countries or more based on customary oaths by the ancestors. J. Chr. Ruhlessin also revealed that *pela* is the only traditional institution that requires regular contact between two groups at a village level. When a Muslim country assists *pela* Christian groups or on the contrary, this assist is not only about an ordinary economy but this is also a commitment for the people interest as a whole.

Muslims and Christians are well aware of the differences between them who are motivated by both the religious context and their historical setting. However, these differences can be related to *pela* as a "bridge" of brotherhood. Ambon, penetrates the boundaries of religion, Islam and Christianity. The aspect of appreciation and respect for *pela* members is held to be a unifying value. In the practical aspects of society, the behavior of the *pela* people is very concerned with the existence of *pela* members which have different religions. Muslim-Christian, for example, appear through the involvement of *Pela* people in the celebration of religious holiday, the inauguration of a king, traditional events of the country. Christians who attend the celebration of *Pela* people from the Islamic village, and on the contrary undergo all religious ritual process and occupy certain positions in the mosque and church. Based on this condition, R. Iwamony believes that the positive values contained in *pela*, such as: a sense of brotherhood that transcends differences in cultural

and religious identity, as well as a sense of solidarity and togetherness in joy and sorrow, both to be developed in the social reality of the Maluku people.

However, to strengthen community fraternity in Maluku, R. Iwamony argues that *pela* values that apply exclusively to *pela* members, which are usually culturally involved only around two or three countries (villages), must be expanded to embrace everyone without exception and equal in Maluku. For him, broadening the scope of *pela* members mean allowing all people in Maluku whatever their religion or cultural background experiencing the goodness of these *pela* values.

The hard test of *Pela* brotherhood is felt when the communal conflict struck Ambon. Many pessimistic expressed that local wisdom, such as *pela-gandong*, did not have enough strength to care for the unity of the Ambonese community when the conflict had occurred. Conflicts that were never expected to occur, both by Muslims and Christians. The occurrence of this conflict is described as starting from a personal problem, turning into a communal riot and then turning into a religious issue. As a result, the conflict brought great sorrow to the community, because thousands of people became victims and countless possessions sold out instantly.

The view that considers *pela-gandong* lost its allure turned out not to be the case. Efforts to stop the conflict actually succeeded through the participation of indigenous groups that echoed *pela* as a concept of brotherhood in Maluku. Ichsan Malik argues that government efforts to stop conflicts such as imposing a curfew, sending dozens of army and police battalions, the enactment of civil emergency, Malino meetings have not been able to stop the conflict. Luckily, the community participated to stop the conflict by focusing on the cultural movement, which is trying to reintegrate the Maluku community that has been totally divided and torn to pieces due to religious and ethnic issues. Cultural movements that are well known for peace, such as the *Baku Bae* (reconciling) movement. Through the *bae raw* movement, the concept of *pela* is touted to strengthen the *bae raw* process. This movement is considered successful as a cultural movement, because it can re-explore local wisdom and open space widely to the community to build peace. The big influence of local wisdom for the creation of Maluku peace made Jacky Manuputty, Maluku peace activist, reveal that the local wisdom system provides reconciliation instruments that can be used to build peace in Maluku. This is important considering that many of the weaknesses in the reconciliation effort since the social conflict that struck Maluku in 1999 lie in the poor potential for reconciliation provided by the cultural layers behind the appearance of conflict. The local wisdom in this study is *gandong* between Muslims and Christians of *Siri Sori* in *Saparua* Island, Maluku.

The brotherhood relationship based on blood relations between Muslims and Christians (*gandong*) in *Siri Sori* is interesting to study because it has contributed to the unification of the two communities of different religions, after both guarding and attacking during the Maluku conflict. *Basudara* people especially the two communities are pictured materially with the similarity of clans, such as *Saimima*, *Sopamena*, *Sanaky*, *Sopaheluwakan*, *Pelupessy*, *Sahupala*. Life cooperates with each other, helps each other has been going on throughout the history of the formation of this country. For example, when there is a wedding celebration that occurs in the *saimima* clan in Muslim of *Siri Sori*, the *Saimima* clan in Cristian of *Siri Sori* is involved, and vice versa. Moreover, they are brothers who previously lived in one place, as a community, namely the *Louhata* community History tells the story that the *Louhata* people in their daily lives often carry out the division of tasks in finding some foods, some go to the sea and some go to the forest to process and take forest products or garden products. The results obtained are then distributed evenly according to the number of people living in *paperisa* (small houses with thatched leaves).

Changes began to occur in the building of the *Louhata* community brotherhood when the Dutch government under the authority of the *Verenigde Oost Indische Compagnie* (VOC) came to power in Maluku in the 17th century. They ordered all those who dwelled in the mountains to descend and occupy the coastal areas especially in *Louhatadi Elhau*. During the reign of the General Governor, *Arnold de Vlaming* in 1643 there were no *Louhata* living in the mountains. They all descended and occupied the coastal area of "*Honimua City*". Since occupying the coastal region, the *Louhata* community is divided into two different administrative areas, namely the area inhabited by Christian communities called *Louhata Amalatu* and the area inhabited by Muslim communities is called *Louhata Amapatty*. The division of the *Louhata* community over two groups based on Islam and Christianity, furthermore known as *Siri Sori* (bathing is forbidden), has influenced the tradition of living together by their ancestors.

It is undeniable that after the Louhatta community is divided into two regions, the interests of each group will be prioritized and often lead to conflict between the two. A conflict occurred between them in 1975, it was about young women from Cristian Siri Sori were harassed by Muslim Siri Sori young boys as the cause. Reconciliation of conflicts between these two groups ensued. They can restore relations and revisit one another. However, the conflict between them was still not over. In 1999-2004, the conflict that engulfed Maluku also influenced the existence of these two different religious communities. The relationship between basudara people who had been running after the conflict in 1975 was once again tarnished. The Cristian and their church was burned by the attackers from the Muslim Siri Sori. Nevertheless, the relations between the two communities recovered after the conflict. They returned to live united as the Louhatta community which is thick with the culture of living people. Understanding the brotherhood relations that form the glue of the two communities of different religions is an important thing that must be done in order to get a comprehensive understanding of how the relationship of the people who are built between them. Historical research methods were used to collect and manage sources, and utilized these sources as useful data for explaining the relationship of brotherhood between Muslims and Christians in Siri Sori which is meaningful in order to maintain the integrity and peace of the people in Maluku. This research is also part of the development of the thesis of Johan R. Saimima who studied the Islamic-Christian Relations in Siri Sori.

Result And Discussion

1. Basudara People Relations between Muslims and Christians in Siri Sori

The relationship between Muslims and Cristians of Siri Sori is *gandong*. They understand that their ancestors lived together in a fellowship before the entry of Islam and Christianity in their alliance in the 16th century. Living together as *basudara* with all the activities that have been undertaken by the ancestors of the Siri Sori people in the past was never forgotten by the generation that lives today. The Maluku conflict that attack them and the in the consideration of third person involvement have destroyed the brotherhood relationship of the Muslims and Christians of Siri Sori. This conflict has taken material and psychological toll. Major losses were experienced by Christians Siri Sori. About 300 Christian homes and one church building were burned, only 10 houses and 1 Public Elementary School building and 1 Secondary School building that did not catch fire. Therefore, the Cristian Siri Sori and the emotion had to make a prayer to break up *gandong* relations with Muslims Siri Sori. However, after the conflict began to drown out by the village government leaders and religious leaders of Cristians Siri Sori realized that the action was not right, then they returned to pray to acknowledge that the Muslim Siri Sori were the brothers of the Cristian of Siri Sori.

The 1999-2004 conflict was recognized by the Muslims and Christians of Siri Sori as an event that had disrupted their brotherhood. The hospitality that is often built in every religious event between the two becomes cut off, working together in building houses of worship, Christians help their Muslim brothers to build mosques, and vice versa Muslims help their Christian brothers to build churches that cannot be actualized for a long time. Their emotions become the dominant factor, Muslims of Siri Sori views that Cristian of Siri Sori as the enemy and vice versa. However, this view does not last long in the minds of these two societies. They have the same awareness that conflict does not bring profit but loss of life, material, and psychological. Moreover, it has damaged their brotherhood. Even though, Muslim does not suffer more casualties than Christian, they are not free to search for food at sea and land, and cannot go to the town of Saparua District to buy their daily necessities because they are controlled by Christians. In addition, they can not visit their brothers in Cristian of Siri Sori. By this situation, community and religious leaders from both people began to move together to call for peace in their respective communities.

2. Brotherhood Exclamation of Community Leaders and Religious Figures to Build Peace

Conflicts that have divided the brotherhood of Muslim and Cristian of Siri Sori that cannot be allowed to continue by the leaders of these two community. The religious leaders are calling for the people to build mutual respect and not kill each other as *basudara*. This was welcomed by Muslim parents. They no longer wanted conflict with their siblings in Cristian Siri Sori. For Islamic religious leaders, conflicts that occur in the name of religion are not desired by God. He wants peace between Muslims and Christians in Siri Sori. Muslims are expected to rebuild the relationship with Cristian Siri Sori as a symbol that they are *basudara*.

People. Likewise, religious leaders of Cristian invited their people to no longer build conflicts with their Muslim brother. This awareness process is conveyed during the Sunday worship and sector fellowship worship. It is not just a call, but to strengthen post-conflict brotherhood relations between Muslims and Christians in Siri Sori, Cristian religious leader who works with the village government mediates a collaborative process involving Muslim and Cristian Siri Sori in one committee for the construction of the church building which caught fire because of the conflict. This collaboration has been running before the emergence of social institutions such as Maluku care institutions that work to build peace.

It is like religious leaders, community leaders of the two countries also carry out the same role to call on their citizens to establish a safe and peaceful relationship between the Muslim and Christian communities in Siri Sori as siblings, which have been built since the days of their ancestors. Likewise, the community leaders of Muslim Siri Sori invited their citizens to stop the conflict with the Cristian Siri Sori, as well as giving awareness to their citizens to build good relations with Cristian Siri Sori as gandong. The role of religious leaders and community leaders have had a major influence in building peace among conflicting communities. The relationship of basudara people who have been implanted since the time of their ancestors became a living memory and their inheritance is increasingly actualized in practical actions to build peace in the midst of conflict that engulfs society. This action was seen through the openness of religious leaders, community leaders and members of the Cristian Siri Sori who involved the Muslim Siri Sori to become the committee for the construction of the church building, as well as the Muslim people who were willing to become a committee, even providing material and energy assistance to work for the construction of the church.

3. The Cooperation of Muslims and Christians Siri Sori in Constructing the Peaceful Louhatta Church

It is not easy to restore the people relations conflict in the religion. Every adherent of religion does not hesitate to build enmity with adherents of other religions for the good name of his religion. However, this did not happen to the people of Muslim and Cristian Siri Sori who were involved in the Maluku conflict in the name of the religion. After the conflict began to fade, religious leaders and community leaders began to mobilize Muslims and Christians to revive the culture of Basudara that had prevailed in the time of the ancestors of these two communities, namely cooperation or mutual cooperation. Christian religious leaders who worked with the Siri Sori village government formed a church construction committee and involved Muslim Siri Sori leaders in the committee. In addition, the Muslim Siri Sori gave their energy to lift sand on the beach, lift rocks and cast a church building.

Conclusion

From the description above, it can be concluded that the relationship between Muslim and Cristian Siri Sori is the relation of Basudara people who have been built since their ancestors in the past. Religion can distinguish between these two communities, but the interrelational gandong relationship has become a unifying legacy of both until now. In Maluku, 1999-2004, it became a dark history for Muslim and Cristian Siri Sori. The hatred of Cristian Siri Sori towards the muslim is not limited to words, but the action through prayer of breaking up relatives (gandong) with the Muslim is carried out in the church.

However, the conflict did not break the brotherhood between Muslims and Christians Siri Sori. The conflict that scattered both was overcome by calls for peace made by religious and community leaders from both sides. Islamic religious leaders called for the Muslims to rebuild the relationship with Christians as a sign that they are brother, vice versa. It is not only the call for peace through words, but also cooperation between them in a committee building of Christian church which was burnt by conflict. Cooperation that produces a church building called Louhatta. The name reminds them as a unity of people who originate from one ancestor and live and move together in one place before they are divided into two administrative regions like today.

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